

'All the rights and capacities'?

Chinese naturalisation and colonial mobility

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Amidst Empires: Colonialism, China and the Chinese, 1839–1997

Flinders University, 29 and 30 January 2018

ABSTRACT

When applying for naturalisation, alien residents of the colonies of New South Wales and South Australia sought to be granted 'all the rights and capacities' of a natural-born British subject. Such 'rights and capacities' could include the right to reside in the colony, to own property, to vote and to hold public office, yet for many colonial Chinese it was the right of movement, rather than rights of settlement, that prompted them to become British subjects. Anti-Chinese legislation introduced in New South Wales and South Australia in 1881 provided exemptions for Chinese British subjects, meaning they could enter without paying the £10 poll tax, a facility that resulted in a significant increase in naturalisation applications. By 1888, when Chinese naturalisation ceased, around 950 Chinese in New South Wales and 300 in South Australia (including the Northern Territory) had taken out naturalisation, the majority of these granted in the early 1880s.

This paper examines the relationship between Chinese naturalisation and colonial mobility in late nineteenth century Australia, specifically in New South Wales and South Australia. It focuses on three interconnected stories: the re-introduction of Chinese restriction laws in the 1880s, the case of prominent Adelaide merchant Way Lee, and the second lives of naturalisation certificates used by Chinese to enter Australia. Together these stories demonstrate the dual histories of inclusion and exclusion embodied in the lives of naturalised Chinese colonists, and suggest a new approach to the history of colonial anti-Chinese laws, one that critically examines policies and practices of exclusion and discrimination while also acknowledging the agency and enterprise of Chinese colonists.

BIOGRAPHY

Dr Kate Bagnall is an ARC DECRA Research Fellow in the School of Humanities and Social Inquiry at the University of Wollongong, where she is working on a comparative study of Chinese colonial citizenship in Australia, Canada and New Zealand. Kate has published on various aspects of Chinese Australian history and is co-editor, with Sophie Couchman, of *Chinese Australians: Politics, Engagement and Resistance* (Brill 2015). Before joining the University of Wollongong in 2016, Kate worked as a writer and editor in the Australian Public Service and as a freelance historian in Canberra. Her earlier research has been supported by fellowships from the Australian Academy of the Humanities, the National Archives of Australia and the National Museum of Australia. She is [@baibi](#) on Twitter and you can find her blog at www.chineseaustralia.org.

1. Chinese seeking citizenship in colonial Australia, New Zealand and Canada 1860 to 1920

Before I begin I would like to acknowledge that we are meeting today on the traditional lands of the Kurna people and I'd like to pay my respect to Elders past, present and future.

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These are, to the best of my knowledge, the last colonial naturalisation certificates granted to Chinese residents in New South Wales and South Australia. On the left is the certificate of 21-year-old gardener Jimmy Ah Moy, granted to him in New South Wales in November 1887. On the right is the certificate of 25-year-old Choy Heung (蔡杏 choi hahng), granted in January 1887.¹ With these certificates Jimmy Ah Moy and Choy Heung were granted 'all the rights and capacities' of a natural-born British subject. I have yet to uncover much about Jimmy Ah Moy, but Choy Heung's story is, I think, a nice place to begin this paper on Chinese naturalisation and colonial mobility.

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When Choy Heung applied for naturalisation in South Australia in 1886 he had only been resident there for a year, but he had been living in Australia for longer. He first arrived in Sydney in 1882, and from there had gone to live in the west of New South Wales at Wilcannia and then Silverton, where he was a cook. He subsequently worked as a cook on a boat trading on the Darling River between Silverton and Adelaide, during which time he became naturalised. Choy Heung returned to Silverton in 1890, working a garden in partnership with his brother. In about 1896, Choy Heung returned to China, where he remained for the next 17 years. When he landed in Sydney again in September 1913, he used his naturalisation certificate – and the word of Sydney merchant William Yinson Lee – as evidence of his right to return to Australia.² His plan was to go back to his brother's garden at Silverton.

In the 19th and early 20th centuries, Chinese Australians like Choy Heung were mobile, travelling back and forth between Australia and Hong Kong and their home counties in the Pearl River Delta for reasons of work, family and education. But within Australia itself they also moved across colonial borders, especially those who lived in areas like the Riverina and the lower Darling and Murray basins. In Choy Heung's case, his work as a cook on a riverboat seems to have taken him between New South Wales and South Australia, as it did another, better-known naturalised Chinese, riverboat captain John Egge, who was naturalised in New South Wales in 1868 and whose statue now stands at the wharf in Wentworth, his home for many years.³

In my paper today I'm going to discuss the relationship between colonial citizenship and mobility in the lives of men like Choy Heung and John Egge, focusing on the history of nineteenth-century

¹ CHOY HEUNG; cook of Adelaide; native of Canton, China; age 25 y; in SA 1 y; Memorial 23-11-1886 signed in Chinese script; Oath 4-1-1887; Certificate 17-1-1887; Note(s) Also landed 8-9-1913 Sydney; Source(s) GG 20-1-1887, A711, A733 (v35).

² NAA: A1, 1914/5252.

³ <http://adb.anu.edu.au/biography/egge-john-12902>.

Chinese naturalisation in the British colonies of New South Wales and South Australia. In Chinese Australian history, we don't often think of the histories of these two colonies side by side. New South Wales and Victoria, yes. And Victoria and South Australia, yes. But New South Wales and South Australia, not so much. In fact, there is comparatively little written about the history of the Chinese in South Australia at all, so I have really been enjoying my foray into the South Australian side of this paper. That said, South Australian history is quite new to me, and I'm still working through many of the questions discussed in the paper, so I welcome your comments and the discussion that will follow directly after my paper and over the next two days. I might also add that the paper differs a little from the abstract.

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This paper comes out of work I have been doing as an ARC DECRA Research Fellow at the University of Wollongong. In my DECRA project, titled 'Chinese seeking citizenship in Australia, New Zealand and Canada, 1860 to 1920', I am looking at the history of colonial Chinese naturalisation, focusing on New South Wales in comparison with British Columbia and New Zealand, as well as the other Australian colonies. The research has three main themes:

1. *Law, policy and political discourse*: What were the laws and policies concerning naturalisation of Chinese settlers? How did these change over time? How did these laws and policies differ between colonial sites? How did naturalisation and aliens laws intersect with anti-Chinese laws?
2. *Naturalised Chinese – who, why and how*: Who were the Chinese men who took out naturalisation and what can we know about their lives (age, length of residence, place of residence, occupation, family status, etc)? Why did they become naturalised? What were the administrative processes for naturalisation?
3. *Contested moments in colonial Chinese citizenship*: What did naturalisation mean to Chinese colonists? When and why did Chinese naturalisation become an issue of public debate and discussion? How did naturalised Chinese participate in discussions around citizenship, and respond to the erosion or removal of their civic rights as British subjects?

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The naturalisation of Chinese migrants in the British settler colonies of Australia, New Zealand and Canada has not been widely discussed in the historiography, other than when it is parcelled into discussions of anti-Chinese laws and policies. Naturalisation of Chinese was disallowed for significant periods between the late 19th century and the middle decades of the 20th century in each of the settler colonial sites I am examining, and this is the dominant narrative we hear in existing histories. As Kim Rubenstein has noted, colonial anxieties over 19th-century Chinese immigration were central to the evolution of Australian citizenship law, and the histories of racial exclusion and citizenship are closely interrelated.

Yet many of the Chinese merchant elite in Australia – men who were leaders in their local Chinese communities and intermediaries with the wider British/European community, like Quong Tart and George On Lee in Sydney and Way Lee in Adelaide – were British subjects by naturalisation, or by birth in Australia or other British colonies. And many of the descendants of 19th-century Chinese migrants that I meet tell me that their great-grandfather or great-great-grandfather was naturalised. I therefore want to examine Chinese naturalisation beyond the context of Chinese exclusion – as something of a dual history of exclusion and inclusion – where due consideration is given to the time when Chinese could be naturalised, and to the ways that British subjecthood affected their experience of colonial life, including in later periods when anti-Chinese laws and policies were powerfully in force.

It's really when we look at the lives of individual Chinese settlers that this dual history is most apparent. In the project I'm therefore looking to link legislation with lives, to think about how ideas about Chinese migration and settlement were translated into law, how law was translated into policy, and how policy affected the lives of individual Chinese Australians. With a shift over the past two decades to consider more of the aspirations, motivations and perspectives of Chinese Australians in the histories we write about them, sometimes histories of anti-Chinese laws and policies, histories of the White Australia policy and its antecedents, can seem a bit outdated. I would argue however that it is still important to understand the way that colonial and federal laws around migration and citizenship shaped the lives of Chinese Australians – because they did, in some very fundamental ways. What we can do differently from the past, however, is to produce agent-driven histories where we seek to understand what Chinese Australians have done, not just what has been done to them.

2. Nationality and naturalisation in the Australian colonies

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Until the introduction of the Australian Citizenship Act in 1948, when the concept of Australian citizen was introduced, residents of Australia were divided into the legal categories of 'British subject' and 'alien'. There are others here today who are much better versed in the legal history of aliens and citizenship in Australia, but for those of you who aren't, I hope a little bit of background will be helpful before I go on to talk more specifically about Chinese naturalisation. Australia's laws regarding naturalisation fitted within the framework of British law, with major British nationality laws introduced in 1844, 1870 and 1914. However, each of the Australian colonies, which became self-governing in the 1850s (except Western Australia), passed its own aliens and naturalisation laws, which, as you can see from this table of New South Wales and South Australian legislation, varied somewhat according to local needs and circumstances. With Federation in 1901, the naturalisation and aliens powers passed to the Commonwealth, with the first federal naturalisation law enacted in 1903.

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Colonial naturalisation and aliens laws provided the mechanisms by which non-British migrants to the colonies could become British subjects. For example, under the New South Wales Naturalization Act of 1875, the applicant had to have been resident in New South Wales for five years and be intending to continue to reside there. The applicant had to present a statutory declaration stating his name, age, birthplace, occupation, and place of residence, as well as a declaration from someone else as to his length of residence and intention to continue residing in the colony. The Governor could approve or deny the application; he was not required to give any reason for the decision and there was no right of appeal. Once a naturalisation certificate was issued, it was not valid until the applicant had sworn an oath of allegiance before a judge, police magistrate or justice of the peace.

The Act also required a record of all naturalisations to be kept centrally. In the project I am using the memorials for naturalisation submitted by applicants, as well as duplicate certificates that were kept on file, to build a database of naturalised Chinese colonists. Having spent some time last year working through the British Columbia naturalisation records, I am very pleased to report that the records here are more fruitful in terms of the information they provide and much better organised than those in BC!

Between 1857 and 1887, a period of thirty years, I estimate that about 950 Chinese were naturalised in New South Wales, and between 1871 and 1887, a period of 16 years, around 300 Chinese were naturalised in South Australia, including the Northern Territory.

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The actual numbers are a bit rubbery, and I'm still working on precise numbers overall, but this table shows the figures compiled by Paul Jones, based on published statistical reports. You can see that Victoria by far had the largest number – also outdoing British Columbia, where I've located just over 1900 Chinese naturalisations to 1915.

In considering the situation of Indigenous Australians in particular, John Chesterman has argued that being a British subject in colonial and early 20th-century Australia had little substantive value, particularly for people who were not white, because of a deliberate separation between formal citizenship status and entitlement to rights and benefits.⁴ At that time not all British subjects were granted the same citizenship rights, such as the right to vote or the duty to serve on a jury, with distinctions being made depending upon wealth, gender, social background and, importantly for our discussion, race. So, while naturalised Chinese and Australian-born Chinese were formally British subjects, specifically racist laws and policies ensured them a less-than-equal legal status.

⁴ Chesterman and Galligan, *Defining Australian Citizenship*, p. 8.

3. Chinese restriction laws in New South Wales and South Australia

[SLIDE on NSW]

[SLIDE on SA]

Table of laws on Chinese immigration in NSW and then SA. Run through the history of this legislation briefly.

4. Chinese naturalisation in the 1880s

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[SLIDE on 1881 and 1888 Acts NSW]

[SLIDE on NSW naturalisations over time]

[SLIDE on NSW reasons for naturalisation]

5. The second life of naturalisation certificates

For the final part of my talk today I want to speak briefly about a second life of naturalisation certificates, which came about through their ongoing and at times fraudulent use to enter Australia in the 1890s and then post-Federation. After the introduction of the 1880s anti-Chinese laws, naturalisation certificates were one of the principal ways that Chinese entered the colonies, as my first example of Choy Heung did in 1913.

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A return prepared by the New South Wales Collector of Customs in 1894, for example, showed the arrival and departure of Chinese between June 1888 and May 1894. Of the 181 Chinese who landed at Sydney during this time, 4 were British born, 7 held exemption papers, 15 were new arrivals who paid the poll tax, and 155 held naturalisation certificates.⁵ Figures into the early 1900s continue to show similar high rates of entry on naturalisation certificates.⁶

According to NSW Customs officials, naturalisation certificates were also the favourite way to attempt to enter the colony fraudulently to avoid paying the poll tax. As early as the mid-1880s,

⁵ "THE INFLUX OF CHINESE." *The Daily Telegraph (Sydney, NSW : 1883 - 1923)* 12 June 1894: 4. Web. 27 Jan 2018 <<http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article236144995>>.

⁶ See population figures for NSW published in the *Government Gazette*, c1897 to 1904 (in Trove).

authorities were already suspicious of those presenting naturalisation certificates on arrival due to the difficulties of positively identifying the certificate's true owner.⁷

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Unlike documents issued to Chinese specifically for identification purposes – such as later exemption certificates issued under colonial and post-Federation immigration restriction laws – naturalisation certificates included no physical description or photograph.

Ability to sign their name in English, spoken English language ability and knowledge of the colony were therefore ways that Customs officials – and in New South Wales this usually meant J.T.T. Donohoe, who was 'Chinese Inspector' in Sydney throughout the 1890s and continued in a similar role until the 1920s – they were ways that Customs officials like Donohoe determined the validity of claims of re-entry on naturalisation certificates. A residence of 5 years in the colony was necessary to be granted naturalisation, and so it was assumed that anyone who tried to enter on a naturalisation certificate would be able to speak some English and know something about the place they had formerly resided in New South Wales. In public statements made by Customs in defence of their efficiency in administering the anti-Chinese immigration laws, it was stated that Donohoe had confiscated hundreds of naturalisation certificates.⁸

I believe that these confiscated certificates might be the 'cancelled' naturalisation certificates now held in record series A806 in the National Archives in Canberra. The series notes for A806 in RecordSearch include nothing very helpful about the certificates' provenance, but from examining the certificates themselves, and by comparing them with three other series of 'cancelled' naturalisation certificates (A801, Victoria; A804, Tasmania; A805, South Australia), I'm pretty certain that's what they are. The National Archives has arranged the certificates by certificate date order rather than by date of cancellation, but annotations and notes attached to the certificates suggest they were collected in the 1890s and early 1900s; the latest date of confiscation appears to be 1915. I'm still working through the certificates in A806 to decipher the multiple layers of annotations in English, and Chinese, but I'll briefly share with you the story of one certificate, that of market gardener Ah Ick (亞益 a yīk).

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Ah Ick's certificate was issued in June 1884 and was used by him to travel overseas twice, in 1892 and 1909. In 1909 Ah Ick was also granted a Certificate Exempting from Dictation Test before he travelled to China. On both occasions, Customs inspector J.T.T. Donohoe administered some of the

⁷ "IDENTIFICATION OF CHINESE." *The Daily Telegraph* (Sydney, NSW : 1883 - 1923) 5 February 1886: 5. Web. 27 Jan 2018 <<http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article237242904>> .

⁸ "THE CHINESE IN AUSTRALIA." *The Sydney Morning Herald* (NSW : 1842 - 1954) 5 March 1888: 3. Web. 27 Jan 2018 <<http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article28347316>>; "KEEPING OUT THE ALIEN" *The Daily Telegraph* (Sydney, NSW : 1883 - 1923) 20 September 1898: 5. Web. 27 Jan 2018 <<http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article239471015>>.

paperwork. In 1913 Ah Ick's certificate was presented by a Chinese man on his arrival in Sydney. The man was initially permitted to land, but was later given the Dictation Test by Inspector Donohoe. He failed the test, and so was charged with being a prohibited immigrant under the Immigration Act. When the case came before the Water Police Court, the man, whose name was Wong Ping, presented witnesses who could testify to his previous residence in Australia, prior to Federation. He said that he had arrived in New South Wales in the mid-1890s and had returned to China in 1901 for a 12-month visit, but was then unable to return as planned because he did not have an exemption certificate under the Immigration Restriction Act, which came into force from the beginning of 1902. Hence, after several failed attempts to purchase his passage back from Hong Kong – the shipping companies required proof of right of entry to Australia – he had purchased Ah Ick's naturalisation certificate in China for £20. The magistrate fined Wong Ping £25 for false representation, but allowed him to remain in Australia as he had proved his earlier domicile.⁹

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There is a similar series of 'cancelled' South Australian certificates (A805) but, unlike the NSW series which takes up three Type 1 boxes [HOW MANY CERTIFICATES?], the South Australian series contains only 10 certificates in total. The certificates in both groups of records mostly date from the 1880s, but as the confiscated South Australian certificates show, naturalisation certificates continued to be used for re-entry into the 1920s. Other files in the National Archives also document the legitimate use of naturalisation certificates to secure re-entry over the same period.

So, to conclude.

I've finished my paper today with these 'cancelled' naturalisation certificates because to me their stories encapsulate some of the themes and questions of my larger investigation into Chinese naturalisation in colonial and early post-Federation Australia – questions about the law, policy and administration of Chinese naturalisation; about the lives of the Chinese men who became British subjects; about the significance and meaning of naturalisation to Chinese colonists; and about the relationship of naturalisation to Chinese restriction.

To understand these certificates we need to know about the legal and administrative contexts in which they were initially created and later used; we need to understand the shifting ways that Chinese restriction functioned over time and place; we need to understand the life histories of the

⁹ "WONG PING GOT BACK." *Evening News (Sydney, NSW : 1869 - 1931)* 13 August 1913: 4. Web. 27 Jan 2018 <<http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article114777295>>; "ALIEN'S DICTATION TEST." *The Sun (Sydney, NSW : 1910 - 1954)* 13 August 1913: 4 (FINAL EXTRA). Web. 27 Jan 2018 <<http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article229680541>>; "NOT HIS CERTIFICATE." *The Daily Telegraph (Sydney, NSW : 1883 - 1923)* 14 August 1913: 5. Web. 27 Jan 2018 <<http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article238978113>>. [Also check NAA files on Ah Ick, Wong Ping.]

individuals whose certificates they were; and we need to understand the patterns of Chinese migration, settlement and return.

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I had promised in my abstract to discuss the story of Adelaide merchant Way Lee 葉繡華 (yip sau wah), something that I haven't done, but I will leave you with this photograph of him at Government House in Adelaide in 1901. Way Lee, naturalised in South Australia in 1882 under the name Sou War, was one of the most vocal campaigners in the late 1880s about the rights of naturalised Chinese in Australia prompted by the difficulties he had in negotiating the New South Wales poll tax – you recall that the NSW 1888 Act provided exemptions only for Chinese naturalised in New South Wales. Way Lee had arrived in Sydney in 1874 to live with his uncle Way Kee, a merchant in Lower George Street. On Way Kee's death in 1892, it was said that he was the richest Chinese in New South Wales. As a young man, Way Lee studied in Sydney and Brisbane before arriving in Adelaide in 1880, establishing Way Lee & Co. in Hindley Street, a business that grew to have branch stores in Beltana, Hawker and Quorn, and in Wentworth, Menindee, Wilcannia and Broken Hill in New South Wales, among other places.